

Tracking Conical Intersections with Nonlinear X-Ray Raman Spectroscopy

Deependra Jadoun and Markus Kowalewski*

Department of Physics, Stockholm University,

Albanova University Centre, SE-106 91 Stockholm, Sweden

I. SIGNAL DERIVATION

The signal is defined as the integrated change in the photon number of $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_2$ field[1],

$$S = \int \frac{d}{dt} \langle \hat{N}_{2,s}(t) \rangle dt \quad (\text{S1})$$

where $\hat{N}_{2,s} = \hat{a}_{2,s}^\dagger \hat{a}_{2,s}$ is the photon number operator corresponding to the s^{th} mode of the $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_2$ field operator, and the expectation value in the above equation corresponds to the matter wave function $\psi \otimes \phi$ with ψ being the matter wave function and ϕ being the field wave function. In the Heisenberg picture, the signal expression can be defined as,

$$S = \int \left\langle \frac{d\hat{N}_{2,s,H}(t)}{dt} \right\rangle dt \quad (\text{S2})$$

where H in the subscript represents the Heisenberg picture, with an operator \hat{A} is defined as $\hat{A}_H = \hat{\mathcal{U}}^\dagger(-\infty, t) \hat{A} \hat{\mathcal{U}}(-\infty, t)$ in Heisenberg picture, and $\hat{\mathcal{U}}(-\infty, t)$ being the time-evolution operator. Using Heisenberg's equation of motion, the integrand in the signal expression reads,

$$\frac{d\hat{N}_{2,s,H}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{N}_{2,s}, \hat{H}_{int}]_H \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$[\hat{N}_{2,s}, \hat{H}_{int}]_H = 2i\Im\{\hat{\alpha}_H \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{2,H}^\dagger(t) \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{1,H}(t)\} \quad (\text{S4})$$

* E-mail: markus.kowalewski@fysik.su.se

Thus, the signal reads,

$$S = \int \left\langle \frac{d\hat{N}_{2,s,H}(t)}{dt} \right\rangle dt = \frac{2}{\hbar} \Im \int dt \left\langle \hat{\alpha}_H \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{2,H}^\dagger(t) \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{1,H}(t) \right\rangle \quad (\text{S5})$$

Converting the above equation to the interaction picture with respect to the matter Hamiltonian \hat{H}_0 and the field Hamiltonian \hat{H}_F ,

$$S = \frac{2}{\hbar} \Im \int dt \left\langle \hat{\alpha}_I \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{2,I}^\dagger(t) \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{1,I}(t) \right\rangle \quad (\text{S6})$$

with,

$$\hat{\alpha}_I(t) = \hat{\mathcal{U}}_0^\dagger(-\infty, t) \hat{\alpha} \hat{\mathcal{U}}_0(-\infty, t) \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$|\psi_I(t)\rangle = \hat{\mathcal{U}}_I(-\infty, t) |\psi_0\rangle \quad (\text{S8})$$

where "I" in the subscript represents the interaction picture. The further derivation is treated in the interaction picture; hence the subscript "I" is omitted, and operators and wave functions are in the interaction picture until stated otherwise. Since the electric fields are considered to be in a coherent state, solving Eq. S6 for the field wave functions corresponding to $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_0$ and $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_1$,

$$S = \frac{2}{\hbar} \Im \int dt \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_2^*(t) \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_1(t) \left\langle \alpha \hat{\alpha}(t) \right\rangle \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$S(\omega_R, \tau_1) = \frac{2}{\hbar} \Im \int dt e^{i\omega_R(t-\tau_1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_2^*(\omega_R) \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_1(t - \tau_1) \left\langle \hat{\alpha}(t) \right\rangle \quad (\text{S10})$$

The perturbative expansion of the matter wave function for the resonant dump-pulse yield,

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = |\psi_0\rangle - \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' (\hat{\mathcal{E}}_0(t') + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_0^\dagger(t')) (\hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') + \hat{\mu}_{01}(t')) |\psi_0\rangle \quad (\text{S11})$$

Using the above equation, the signal expression reads,

$$\begin{aligned} S(\omega_R, \tau_1) = & \frac{2}{\hbar} \Im \int dt e^{i\omega_R(t-\tau_1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_2^*(\omega_R) \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_1(t - \tau_1) \\ & \left\{ -\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \left\langle \hat{\alpha}(t) (\hat{\mathcal{E}}_0(t') + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_0^\dagger(t')) (\hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') + \hat{\mu}_{01}(t')) \right\rangle \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \left\langle (\hat{\mathcal{E}}_0(t') + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_0^\dagger(t')) (\hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') + \hat{\mu}_{01}(t')) \hat{\alpha}(t) \right\rangle \right\} \quad (\text{S12}) \end{aligned}$$

Considering $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_0(t')$ field photons to be in a coherent state and solving for the corresponding field wave functions,

$$S(\omega_R, \tau_1) = \frac{2}{\hbar} \Im \int dt e^{i\omega_R(t-\tau_1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_2^*(\omega_R) \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_1(t - \tau_1) \left\{ -\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \mathcal{E}_0(t') \cos(\omega_0 t') \right. \\ \left. \left[\langle \psi_0 | \hat{\alpha}(t) [\hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') + \hat{\mu}_{01}(t')] | \psi_0 \rangle - \langle \psi_0 | [\hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') + \hat{\mu}_{01}(t')] \hat{\alpha}(t) | \psi_0 \rangle \right] \right\} \quad (\text{S13})$$

$$S(\omega_R, \tau_1) = \frac{2}{\hbar} \Im \int dt e^{i\omega_R(t-\tau_1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_2^*(\omega_R) \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_1(t - \tau_1) \left\{ -\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_0(t') \cos(\omega_0 t') \right. \\ \left[\langle \psi_0 | \hat{\alpha}_I(t) \hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') | \psi_0 \rangle - \langle \psi_0 | \hat{\mu}_{01}(t') \hat{\alpha}(t) | \psi_0 \rangle \right] \\ \left. + \left[\langle \psi_0 | \hat{\alpha}(t) \hat{\mu}_{01}(t') | \psi_0 \rangle - \langle \psi_0 | \hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') \hat{\alpha}(t) | \psi_0 \rangle \right] \right\} \quad (\text{S14})$$

The correlation functions are complex conjugates of each other, thus,

$$S(\omega_R, \tau_1) = \frac{4}{\hbar^2} \Im \int dt e^{i\omega_R(t-\tau_1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_2^*(\omega_R) \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_1(t - \tau_1) \Im \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_0(t') \cos(\omega_0 t') \right. \\ \left. \left[\langle \psi_0 | \hat{\alpha}(t) \hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') | \psi_0 \rangle + \langle \psi_0 | \hat{\alpha}(t) \hat{\mu}_{01}(t') | \psi_0 \rangle \right] \right\} \quad (\text{S15})$$

The final expression is given by,

$$S(\omega_R, \omega_0, \tau_1, \tau_0) = \frac{4}{\hbar^2} \Im \int dt e^{i\omega_R(t-\tau_1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_2^*(\omega_R) \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_1(t - \tau_1) \times \\ \left\{ \Im \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_0(t' - \tau_0) \cos(\omega_0(t' - \tau_0)) \langle \psi_0 | \hat{\alpha}(t) [\hat{\mu}_{01}^\dagger(t') + \hat{\mu}_{01}(t')] | \psi_0 \rangle \right\} \quad (\text{S16})$$

II. MODEL SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Atomic units ($\hbar = e = m_e = 4\pi\epsilon_0 = 1$) are used hereafter until stated otherwise. The following expressions were used to construct the diabatic potential energy surfaces and the diabatic couplings

Figure S1. The nuclear coordinates dependent adiabatic electronic state separation is shown here. The red dot at $R_1=2$ Bohr represents the CI. Gray contours on the plot show the energy separation between adiabatic electronic states in different regions.

as a function of reaction coordinates R_0 and R_1 ,

$$f_1(R_2) = R_2^2$$

$$f_1(R_1, x_h, x_v) = (R_1 - x_h)^2 + x_v$$

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{27.211} [f_0(R_1, 2, 0) + f_2(R_2)]$$

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{27.211} [f_0(R_1, 3.1, 3.2) + f_2(R_2)] \quad (\text{S17})$$

$$c_0(R_1, \gamma, \beta_1, x_c) = \gamma e^{-\beta_1(R_1 - x_c)^2}$$

$$c_1(R_2, \beta_2) = \left(1 - e^{-|\beta_2 R_2|}\right) \times \left(1 - \left|\frac{R_2 - |R_2|}{|R_2|}\right|\right)$$

$$C_{01} = c_1(R_1, 0.007, 5.5, 4) \times c_2(R_2, 2)$$

where R_1 and R_2 represent reaction coordinates, V_0 and V_1 represent diabatic electronic states, and C_{01} represents diabatic couplings between the electronic states. Figure S1 shows the adiabatic electronic state separation, which depends on the nuclear coordinates R_1 and R_2 . Gray contours are drawn in the plot to show the separation between the electronic states. The red dot at $R_1=2$ Bohr represents the CI.

Figure S2. Wave packet dynamics on potential energy surfaces. (a) 1D curves of wave packets (dashed curves) on the potential energy curves (solid) at the time delay of ≈ 48 fs. (b) The population dynamics plot with the black dot shows the time delay corresponding to the positions of wave packets in (a).

III. APPROXIMATION FOR TIME-VARYING ELECTRONIC STATE SEPARATION

Since the conical intersection (CI) relevant dynamics takes place on the V_1 state before the passage through the CI, the changing energy separation between the electronic states is constructed using the diabatic nuclear wave packets on the V_1 state. The expression used for the calculation of changing energy separation is,

$$dV(t) = \frac{|\langle \psi_1(t) | V_1 | \psi_1(t) \rangle - \langle \psi_1(t) | V_0 | \psi_1(t) \rangle|}{|\langle \psi_1(t) | \psi_1(t) \rangle|}. \quad (\text{S18})$$

Since the wave packets in the V_1 state are well-localized before and near the CI, as shown in Fig. S2, the approximate electronic state separation given by Eq. S18 is valid. However, Eq. S18 cannot be used to approximate electronic state separation once the wave packets are de-localized, and both the electronic states are populated.

Figure S3. Raman signals for fixed dump-pulse delay (type (i) signals) after the nuclear wave packet has passed through the CI: (a) The signal for dump-pulse delay $\tau_0=95$ fs and the frequency $\omega_0=2$ eV. (b) The signal for dump-pulse delay $\tau_0=75$ fs and the frequency $\omega_0=2$ eV. The phase relation of the signal with the dump pulse represents the process which creates the superposition of electronic states. In (a), the superposition is created by the stimulated emission of the dump-pulse photons, whereas in (b), the superposition is created by the absorption of the photons. The other parameters of the dump-pulse and the Raman probe are: $\sigma_0=2$ fs, $\sigma_1=0.5$ fs, and $\sigma_2=0.5$ fs.

IV. ADDITIONAL SPECTRA

A. Signal (i) : $S'(\tau_1; \omega_0, \tau_0)$

When the system has already passed through the CI, the dump-pulse will interact with an intrinsically generated superposition. Thus, the phase of the dump-pulse relative to the coherence will result in either absorption or stimulated emission. Hence, for a specific dump-pulse frequency and delay, the signal may be dominated by the stimulated emission over the absorption of dump-pulse photons or vice versa. Spectra with $\omega_0=2$ eV at $\tau_0=95$ fs and $\tau_0=75$ fs are shown along with the dump-pulse in Fig. S3(a) and (b), respectively. In Fig. S3(a), the signal and the dump-pulse are in phase, and the signal originates from the stimulated emission of the dump-pulse photons. The signal in Fig. S3(b) is out of phase with the dump pulse, and the dump-pulse photons are absorbed. Therefore,

Figure S4. Spectra similar to Fig. 5(b) in the paper are shown here for (a) $\omega_0=2$ eV, (b) $\omega_0=3$ eV, and (c) $\omega_0=4$ eV. The white-dashed curve represents the electronic state separation approximated using the wave packets in the V_1 state. Other pulse parameters: $\sigma_0=2$ fs, $\sigma_1=0.5$ fs, and $\sigma_2=0.5$ fs.

the information regarding the process that creates a coherent superposition of the electronic states, i.e., the absorption or the stimulated emission of the dump-pulse photons, is contained in the Raman signal.

B. Signal (iii): $S''(\omega_1, \tau_0; \omega_0)$

Spectra similar to Fig. 4(b) in the paper are shown here. In Fig. S4(a), a dump-pulse with $\omega_0=2$ eV is used to create an electronic coherence. The spectrum shows that the system is resonant with the dump-pulse frequency between 20 fs and 40 fs, with the peak intensity at ≈ 30 fs. After the passage through the CI, a signal appears after 80 fs with a lower intensity compared to the signal between 20 fs and 40 fs. The decrease in the signal intensity can be considered a feature of

Figure S5. Dump pulse delay- and frequency-dependent Raman signals: (a) The signal contribution for the superposition created from the wave functions initially in the V_0 state due to dump-pulse interaction. (b) The signal contribution for the superposition created from the wave functions initially in the V_1 state. The dashed blue curve shows the time-dependent electronic state separation. Solid and dashed contour curves represent the signal with the positive and negative intensity, respectively. The other parameters of the dump-pulse and the Raman probe are: $\sigma_0=3$ fs, $\sigma_1=0.5$ fs, $\sigma_2=0.5$ fs, and $\tau_1=0$ fs.

population transfer and delocalization of the wave packets. Figures S4(b) and (c) show the signal with dump-pulse frequencies of 3 eV and 4 eV, respectively, and the features similar to Fig. S4(a) can be seen.

C. Signal $S'(\omega_0, \tau_0; \tau_1)$

Another version of the signal, $S'(\omega_0, \tau_0; \tau_1)$, is shown here which fixes the Raman probe delay, but scans the dump pulse delay and varies the dump pulse center frequency parametrically. It tracks the evolving energy separation between the electronic states, but does not contain any useful information about the evolution of the coherent superposition. Spectra in Fig. S5 show the behavior of the signal as a function of ω_0 and τ_0 . The total spectrum is a sum of four elements in the polarizability matrix,

but signals originating from the two off-diagonal elements that have a major contribution to the signal are shown here separately for understanding. Figure S5(a) shows the signal in which the coherent superposition with the V_1 state is created using the V_0 state wave functions when the dump-pulse interaction takes place. Similarly, Fig. S5(b) shows the signal in which the coherent superposition with the V_0 state is created using the wave functions in the V_1 state when the dump-pulse interacts with the system. In Fig. S5(a), a signal with negative intensity appears around 4 eV and corresponds to the ground state population remaining after the pumping process. The negative intensity of the signal indicates that the coherent superposition is generated via the absorption of the dump-pulse photons. The signal below 3 eV appears only after 40 fs when the population transfer takes place from the V_1 state to the V_0 state. The signal below 1 eV starts with the negative intensity when the population transfer from state V_1 to state V_0 begins in the vicinity of the CI. The intensity of the signal changes from negative to positive when the wave packets arrive in the region where the state V_0 becomes higher in energy than state V_1 after the CI. After 60 fs, the signal intensity changes to negative again when the wave packets move away from the CI region in the V_0 state. Two distinct signals appear at ≈ 70 fs and ≈ 80 fs since the V_1 state population is transferred twice to the V_0 state via the CI. In Fig. S5(b), a signal with the positive intensity appears at decreasing ω_0 with increasing τ_0 , indicating that the wave packets are moving continuously on the V_1 state towards the CI, and the coherent superposition is generated by the stimulated emission of the dump-pulse photons. The signal intensity changes from positive to negative between 50 fs and 75 fs due to the wave packets being in the region where the V_1 state is lower in energy compared to the V_0 state. The signal follows the blue-dashed curve, which shows the time-varying separation between the electronic states.

A combined spectrum of Figs. S5(a) and (b) along with the diagonal elements of the polarizability matrix is shown in Fig. S6(b). Since only 30% population is transferred from the V_1 to V_0 state near the CI in parts, the spectrum is dominated by the coherent superposition created with the V_0 state using the wave functions in the V_1 state. To show the features of the coherent superposition with the V_1 state created using the wave functions in the V_0 state, a certain region of the spectrum is magnified five times and is indicated by a green-dashed boundary in Fig. S6(a). Due to a fixed Raman probe delay, the signal only captures the immediate wave function overlap created by the dump-pulse, and it shows similar features to a spectrum constructed by the absorption and the stimulated emission

Figure S6. Dump-pulse delay and frequency dependent signals: (a) The Raman signal constructed using Eq. 9, and (b) the absorption and the stimulated emission spectrum of a pulse identical to the dump pulse. The other parameters of the dump-pulse and the Raman probe are: $\sigma_0=3$ fs, $\sigma_1=0.5$ fs, $\sigma_2=0.5$ fs, and $\tau_1=0$ fs.

of the dump-pulse photons (see Ref. [2] for signal expression), shown in Fig. S6(b). The lower limit of the center frequency of the dump-pulse is bound to the width of the dump-pulse and the blind spot in Fig. S6 is similar to the one observed in the transient absorption study of Rhodopsin [3] with optical pulses. The Raman signal obtained by fixing the Raman probe delay produces a spectrum that looks similar to the absorption and the stimulated emission spectrum.

V. COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

A grid with 256×256 points is used for the construction of the energy curves for model system. Our in-house code QDng is used for the wave packet propagation on the energy curves, and the Arnoldi method is implemented for dynamics[4]. The Fourier transform method is used to calculate the second-order derivation for the calculation of the kinetic energy of wave functions. The reduced mass of the system is 50000 a.u., and the time steps are separated by ≈ 48 as in wave function dynamics. The

correlation function in the Eq. S16 is calculated using the direct propagation simulation protocol[5].

- [1] Mukamel, S. *Principles of Nonlinear Optical Spectroscopy*; Oxford series in optical and imaging sciences; Oxford University Press, 1999.
- [2] Kowalewski, M.; Fingerhut, B. P.; Dorfman, K. E.; Bennett, K.; Mukamel, S. Simulating coherent multidimensional spectroscopy of nonadiabatic molecular processes: From the infrared to the x-ray regime. *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117*, 12165–12226.
- [3] Polli, D.; Altoe, P.; Weingart, O.; Spillane, K. M.; Manzoni, C.; Brida, D.; Tomasello, G.; Orlandi, G.; Kukura, P.; Mathies, R. A., et al. Conical intersection dynamics of the primary photoisomerization event in vision. *Nature* **2010**, *467*, 440–443.
- [4] Arnoldi, W. E. The principle of minimized iterations in the solution of the matrix eigenvalue problem. *Q. Appl. Math.* **1951**, *9*, 17–29.
- [5] Kowalewski, M.; Mukamel, S. Stimulated Raman signals at conical intersections: Ab initio surface hopping simulation protocol with direct propagation of the nuclear wave function. *J Chem. Phys.* **2015**, *143*, 044117.